

Real-time blind controllers for cost-efficient Water Supply Systems operation: a comparative study

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ABSTRACT

Efficient operation of water supply systems (WSS) is increasingly critical due to rising energy costs, water resource availability, demands variability, and the growing complexity of water network infrastructure. A significant share of operational expenses in WSS stems from energy consumption, particularly in systems that rely on pumping to meet demand and maintain service levels [1].

Traditional control strategies typically use fixed tank level setpoints defined by water utilities. However, these approaches often ignore variable energy prices and the dynamic capabilities of variable-speed pumps (VSPs), resulting in suboptimal energy performance [1,2]. Recent research [3,4,5] has introduced model predictive control-based methods that combine accurate demand forecasting with advanced optimization algorithms to determine cost-efficient pump schedules and tank level management. While promising, these methods depend heavily on forecast accuracy, a major challenge in real-world WSS subject to manual interventions or unpredictable consumption patterns. Consequently, optimization may fail to deliver practical, robust solutions.

This paper introduces real-time blind controllers (control strategies that operate without relying on demand forecasts) for cost-energy efficient WSS operation. These controllers use real-time WSS data, mainly tank levels, to make operational decisions while respecting constraints such as minimum and maximum tank levels. They dynamically adjust VSP operation to minimize energy costs and, in some cases, incorporate short-term predictive heuristics based on historical patterns or price signals.

The study presents a comparative analysis of three blind control strategies:

- Price-aware threshold-based control: A simple yet robust method that triggers pump operation based on predefined tank level thresholds, dynamically adjusted according to time-of-use (TOU) energy tariffs to prioritize pumping during low-cost periods while ensuring service reliability.

- Hybrid blind-predictive control: An advanced approach that integrates limited predictive elements, such as short-term tank level trends, into the control logic to improve cost efficiency without requiring demand forecasts.
- Data-driven control: A machine learning-based strategy that predicts control actions using historical data, enhancing adaptability and cost efficiency under uncertain conditions.

Each controller is evaluated using a benchmark WSS model under diverse operational scenarios, including high demand variability and manual interventions. Performance metrics include total energy cost, compliance with tank level constraints, and computational efficiency.

Results show that blind controllers achieve competitive performance compared to model predictive control (MPC), particularly in environments where demand forecasting is unreliable or infeasible. Key findings indicate that blind controllers offer a favorable balance between robustness and cost efficiency. They are less sensitive to forecast errors, adapt effectively to unexpected changes, and maintain low computational complexity, making them suitable for real-time deployment in decision support tools or supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) systems.

This study contributes to the development of resilient and adaptive control strategies for WSS. By eliminating dependency on demand forecasts, blind controllers provide a practical and scalable solution for utilities facing operational uncertainty. This represents a promising approach for cost-energy efficient and resilient WSS operation. Their ability to function effectively under uncertainty, combined with minimal computational requirements, makes them particularly attractive for utilities with limited access to high-quality demand data. Future work will explore integration with digital twin environments and hybrid MPC approaches to further enhance performance.

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